

EDİTÖRE MEKTUP

LETTER TO EDITOR

**NATIONAL EARLY WARNING SCORE AND CHARLSON
COMORBIDITY INDEX****Assoc. Prof. Serdar Özdemir¹, MD, Assoc. Prof. Hatice Şeyma Akça², MD,
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Dear editor,

Vital signs are the simplest and probably the most important information collected about hospitalized patients. A vital sign can be defined as any patient feature that can monitor the patient's progress, predict the specific treatment that should be administered to the patient, or monitor the patient. Some patient characteristics, such as date of birth and gender, are fixed, whereas others, including the four traditional vital signs, are dynamic and can change at any time. Several such features have been proposed as additional vital signs. Pain, dyspnea, oximetry, mental status, functional status, and mobility have all been suggested as vital signs (1).

NEWS (National Early Warning Score) was first established in 2012 by The National Early Warning Score Development and Implementation Group, created by the Royal College of Physicians London, in the UK National Health Service to achieve a high standard of patient care, reduce the mortality rate, and improve acute It was developed to standardize the assessment of diseases (2). This scoring system was developed in the first place in order to determine the sudden worsening of the patients hospitalized in the emergency department, service or intensive care unit in the UK hospitals, to reveal the frequency of follow-up of the patients and to determine which patients should be transferred to the intensive care unit. The NEWS scoring system has spread from the UK to the whole world and has been the subject of studies for patient follow-up and triage (3). In one of the retrospective observational studies on NEWS conducted in 2015, patients diagnosed with sepsis and septic shock were evaluated with the SIRS-based approach, and high sensitivity and specificity were found in terms of sepsis diagnosis in those with a score of 3 and above in NEWS (4).

Anamnesis and comorbidities are another important component of the examination. Comorbidities are an independent risk factor for mortality. Charlson Comorbidity Index is a index based on comorbidities. Charlson comorbidity index is a widely used and accepted index for mortality prediction. It is a mortality indicator created by Mary Charlson et al in 1987 to estimate mortality by classifying comorbid disease states and measuring their severity. It was defined by examining 559 patients hospitalized for 1 year in the New York Hospital internal medicine service and associated comorbidities with one-year all-cause mortality (5). While determining the comorbid factors in the list, the comorbid factors with a relative risk above 1.2 were taken into consideration and 1 point if the relative risk is between 1.2-1.5, 2 points between 1.5-2.5, 3 points between 2.5-3.5, and 6 points if the relative risk is higher than 3.5. evaluated as. Although it was origi-

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nally developed for breast cancer patients, after evaluations, it was shown by Charlson et al. that Charlson Comorbidity Index can be a powerful predictor of disease burden and mortality. The Charlson Comorbidity Index was originally designed to classify prognostic comorbidity in longitudinal studies. The importance of comorbidity was also demonstrated by Greenfield et al. in their study of the comorbidity index, which measures baseline comorbidity severity, acute exacerbations, and patient functional status (6).

The NEWS and Charlson Comorbidity Index are indices calculated with different parameters. A single index may not be sufficient for clinicians to make clinical decisions. Researchers should be encouraged to develop the ideal index for clinical decision making.

REFERENCES

1. Brekke IJ, Puntervoll LH, Pedersen PB, Kellett J, Brabrand M. The value of vital sign trends in predicting and monitoring clinical deterioration: A systematic review. *PLoS One*. 2019 Jan 15;14(1):e0210875.
2. Subbe CP, Kruger M, Rutherford P, Gemmel L. Validation of a modified Early Warning Score in medical admissions. *QJM Mon J Assoc Physicians*. 2001;94(10):521-6.
3. Baines E, Kanagasundaram NS. Early Warning Scores. *Br Med J*. 2006; 23:372-5.
4. Keep JW, Messmer AS, Sladden R, Burrell N, Pinate R, Tunnicliff M, et al. National early warning score at Emergency Department triage may allow earlier identification of 57 patients with severe sepsis and septic shock: a retrospective observational study. *Emerg Med J EMJ*. 2016;33(1):37-41.
5. Gül F, Arslantaş MK, Cinel İ, Kumar A. Changing Definitions of Sepsis. *Turk J Anaesthesiol Reanim*. 2017;45(3):129-38.
6. Greenfield S, Blanco DM, Elashoff RM, Ganz PA. Patterns of care related to age of breast cancer patients. *JAMA*. 1987 May 22-29;257(20):2766-70.